

Observational capacity inventories: potential uses and specifications

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Introduction

Inventories are a recurring phenomenon in conversations around polar observing coordination. At some level, knowing what is being observed is critical to developing plans and strategies towards better observational coverage, better coordination between observing programs, and more efficient use of limited resources. Developing an inventory of Arctic observing capacities is not a straightforward task: from data system development to simply defining observing capacities, the number of decisions necessary to even begin to inventory observing activities is lengthy.

The Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks' Committee on Networks (SAON CON) was tasked with conducting an inventory of national observing capacity in the 2018 SAON and 2021 SAON CON work plans. Following the re-activation of the SAON CON after the Arctic Council pause, the CON has focused first in figuring out what said inventory should include. To that end, the CON discussed in detail a number of ways that partner organizations maintain and use inventories with smaller scopes, and concluded that a wider survey of use cases was necessary to proceed.

Capturing use cases

In order to capture a wide range of potential use cases, SAON CON set up a [poll](#). This included a number of use cases identified by the Polar Observing Asset Working Group (POAwg)'s, which were developed in the process of building the Registry of Polar Observing Networks (RoPON). Members of CON, the SAON Board, and the USAON Board filled out the poll, and in some cases, shared it with partners to fill out. Respondents filled in detail on several existing use cases, and added new ones..

The poll asked respondents to describe a single use scenario for an inventory, starting with a description of who might use it for what purpose.

The poll then asked about six categories of specifications:

1. **Participation:** who contributes to the inventory
2. **Geographic coverage:** what geographic area is included in the inventory
3. **Thematic contents:** is the inventory specific to a particular discipline/system, or is it broadly inclusive and limited only in geography?
4. **Completeness:** what is the lower limit of completeness that would still serve the purpose?
5. **Time coverage:** is the relevant information about present, future, past, or historical observations?
6. **Level of detail:** what specificity is appropriate for the inventory – does it need to be at the individual site or instrument level, or are broader projects or networks appropriate?

Each question asked about several levels of the specification, having respondents indicate whether that level is insufficient (does not contribute to the goal specified in the use case), necessary, nice to have (more information than is needed), or not necessary (more information than is useful).

To illustrate the responses, we developed a “snowflake diagram”. Each of the six categories of specifications is shown on a leg of the snowflake. The different potential specifications are the segments, in order from the smallest inventory at the inside to the largest inventory at the outside. For each scenario, these specification options are color-coded according to the legend, with options: inadequate (yellow), helpful but not enough (green), necessary (blue), nice but not necessary (pink), and too much to be useful (white). The closer to the center the blue “necessary” band is, the smaller the inventory that is needed to address the goal. For some use cases, “necessary” was determined to cover a range of possible specifications. Those are noted for each use case.

Figure 1: Legend for the snowflake diagrams in the following sections.

Each snowflake has up to two icons in the center: the smiley indicates whether the product needs to be human-readable and the computer indicates whether it needs to be machine-readable.

The six dimensions of use cases are as follows:

Participation describes who is making the observations or providing the observing capacity included in the inventory. Options range from

- Research group (or equivalent) at the smallest scale. For example a list of all of the sites where a research group has equipment deployed.
- Institution refers to an entity consisting of many research groups, which may own/manage one or more sites/vessels/facilities. For example, the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) owns and operates several research vessels, each with many research cruises planned per year (AWI, n.d.).
- National/Member scale participation means that several institutions and research groups contribute to inventory. This might be a catalog of all SNOTEL sites maintained by US institutions (Flemming, 2023), or a system where institutional members contribute to a shared inventory of Svalbard observing sites (SIOS: Christiansen, 2023).
- Regional refers to a multi-national effort. An example would be EU-PolarNet efforts towards an integrated polar observing system (Lymer, 2024).
- Global participation would be everyone working in some aspect of polar science contributing to a single inventory.

Coverage describes the geographic scope of the inventory

- Site-level coverage might refer to a particular research station or community.
- Regional coverage is a fixed non-national area, for example Svalbard or the Frahm Strait area.
- National coverage refers to a country's Arctic territory, e.g., Alaska.
- Pan-Arctic coverage would be observations occurring anywhere in the Arctic.
- Global coverage would extend beyond the Arctic into sub-Arctic (and beyond) latitudes.

Contents refers to the topical scope of what is included in the inventory

- Funder limits would be any observational efforts funded by a particular organization. For example, the Arctic Observing Viewer mapped all in situ observing efforts funded by the US National Science Foundation (Manley, 2015).
- Disciplinary limits would be consistent with traditional academic disciplines, like terrestrial ecology, oceanography, or atmospheric science.
- System limits cross disciplinary boundaries, but with some topical focus. The State of Alaska's Salmon and People (SASAP) project brought together data relevant to the study of salmon across a range of sectors and scientific disciplines (Carothers, 2021).
- Comprehensive would refer to an inventory that includes all topical content, and is instead only limited by the geographic scope (e.g., SIOS: Christiansen, 2023).

Detail is the level of specificity with which entries are included in the inventory

- Network level specificity is effectively an inventory of inventories, where someone is directed to the relevant network to find more detailed information. The Registry of Polar Observing Networks (RoPON) is a network-level inventory.
- Project level specificity is a step more detailed, but individual entries may still include multiple sites, types of observations, or instruments.
- Site-level detail is necessary to fully resolve a map of where observations are being made, which is made complicated by the fact that different observing modalities may have different coverage.
- Instrument-level detail allows an inventory user to find exactly what is being measured and where.

Time specifies whether the inventory includes what has been done already, is ongoing, or is proposed.

- Historical observations would be those that occurred some time before the present. This is often a data discovery tool.
- Past observations are likewise largely used for data discovery, but may also indicate who has recently been working in a particular area.
- Present observations are ongoing projects/efforts, with some indication that they will continue into the near future.

- Future/proposed observations are those in planning stages, where it may still be possible to make adjustments or additions.

Completeness describes what fraction of the observations/observational capacity must be included in the inventory to meet the goals of the scenario.

- $\geq 20\%$ low completeness levels are “highlights” or examples of observing efforts.
- $\geq 50\%$ partial completeness gives an indication of the range of observing activities happening, but there are likely major efforts missing.
- $\geq 80\%$ majority completeness captures most of the activity, but leaves some uncertainty to what else might be going on.
- 100% total completeness is necessary for true gaps analysis.

Use cases

From the 20 responses to the poll, we combined a few duplicates and ended up with 14 distinct use cases. The use cases were each described by respondents to the poll (rather than a pre-selected set of choices) and represent a combination of key uses and scenarios that people could comfortably describe.

We sorted these roughly by the geographic scale of interest (y-axis) and the kind of information that someone would be using an inventory to access (x-axis). These are approximate categorizations, and we show the detailed specifications in the following sections for each according to the number here:

Figure 2: Mapping 14 use cases for inventories over scale and what kind of information is needed.

1. Indigenous Observer

The Indigenous observer case considers someone who is a local expert and contributes observations to a larger effort. They are interested in ongoing work in the region, but as they are not reliant on others for observations, any available information on the contents, completeness, and participation axes is nice to have but not necessary. They are most interested in a site-level inventory relevant to their immediate community, subsistence areas, and the surrounding region. Project-level information is the most helpful, and the primary interest is in current and future efforts.

2. Indigenous or community planner

This use case covers information needs of a community planner, environmental coordinator or administrator for an Indigenous or local government of an Arctic community (e.g., municipality, Tribal Council, regional administration). Observational data and/or metadata about observations of relevance are needed in the context of planning and decision-making at the community scale. These applications include acquisition of funds to support community action in response to a changing environment, such as development of climate adaptation or hazard assessment and mitigation plans or planning for community relocation. The type of information needed would include, e.g., specifics on where and how long-term data are collected on Indigenous/community lands, availability of processed data and derived information products relevant in a community planning context, and identification of critical data gaps.

Depending on the application, the appropriate scope might change slightly. In a case where the community planner needs information about a specific challenge, e.g., coastal erosion, then a smaller inventory could be useful. A list of measurement sites in the area maintained by a research group would meet those needs (snowflake 2A). For a larger set of information needs, like considering risk factors around harmful algal blooms, the community planner would need a more expansive description of available observations (snowflake 2B).

3. Researcher new to a popular site

In this scenario, a researcher who has previously worked in another region has a new project in a popular area. For example, a glaciologist has previously worked on Alaskan glaciers but is collaborating on a project looking at glaciers in Svalbard. They need information about what observations are being made and who is

making them, so as to not re-do work that has already been done. The coverage focus is specific to the site/region, rather than broader, but they benefit from broader participation.

4. Industry operations

This use case relates to tactical or strategic information requirements of industrial operators in a particular locale or region. For example, in the context of surface mineral extraction, a range of variables such as water quality and stream hydrology, various biological parameters capturing impacts of operations, potential impacts on protected species including in a subsistence harvest context are relevant. Highly localized, long-term records of these variables will have to be analyzed, e.g., to determine baseline conditions that would serve as restoration goals for mine reclamation. Furthermore, mine operators would need to collect and track a number of variables that serve as indicators for compliance with environmental regulations. Environmental impact assessments and regulatory documents can help provide in-depth detail of such cases, as illustrated in an analysis of hardrock mines in Alaska (Adams et al., 2025).

5. Remote sensing calibration and validation project

This use case could cover the information needs of a satellite programme. Programmes like Copernicus need *in-situ* data: observations, reference and ancillary data. The need is for the production and validation in satellite based services and for calibration and validation (Cal/Val) of satellite sensors. The Copernicus assessment report [Arctic In Situ Data Availability](#) identifies severe gaps with regards to 1) Central Arctic, 2) Timely availability and quality of observations, 3) Non-European regions, 4) Fit-for-purpose of observation technology, 5) Data management structures, and 6) Sustainability of observing systems. In-situ data comes from a series of data providers and networks at national, regional and global level. Ideally the mentioned gaps should be closed in collaboration with data providers. There are, however, cases where satellite programmes may want an overview of observing efforts in the Arctic order in to pursue new data

providers or sources. Satellite programmes are interested in data from very specific disciplines. The information must be machine readable.

6. Early career researcher

Early career researchers particularly benefit from inventories of observing activities and capacity. With multiple responses regarding this scenario in the poll, we included two snowflakes here with two different versions of this scenario. The top one, for an ECR working in a field where widespread coverage is important, requires a much larger inventory. This scenario could be a postdoctoral researcher writing their first major proposal with plans for field measurements in several locations. This scenario – where observing activities are occurring across a large area by many Arctic and non-Arctic actors – has a very large scope for contributions. Proposing a new observing activity requires knowing what is currently being observed in order to not duplicate efforts, which makes completeness important. The second version of the scenario is an ECR working on a more site-specific project. This could be a graduate student interested in ecological responses to severe weather events in the area around Toolik Research Station. Here there are much lower requirements for participation, where activity is largely national, and very narrow coverage requirements. The tradeoff is that there are higher requirements for detail, with site level activity descriptions necessary.

Early career researchers benefit from inventories filling gaps in awareness that for a more senior researcher would be filled by experience, networks, and familiarity with ongoing activities. Students rely on their advisors for this kind of information, but where an advisor is too busy or works in a related but adjacent topic/site, early career researchers lose a lot of time to data discovery and finding related projects.

7. Researcher new to a field

Similar to the scenario with new early career researchers, senior researchers occasionally shift fields of research over their careers. Perhaps someone has developed a new remote sensing approach that has wider applications, or simply interests have shifted over time. Either way, senior researchers moving into a new area have the benefit of experience with the research enterprise, but they still need to know what is being observed and by whom. They benefit from widespread participation in an inventory, with project to site-level detail. Depending on the area of interest, coverage may be more limited with regional coverage appropriate for most applications, though some areas may require national or pan-Arctic inventories.

8. Funder interested in a particular question

Funders of science and observing may want to support projects related to the Arctic, usually within specific disciplines. Traditionally such funding has been organised at the national level, but there is an increasing interest among national funders to seek to coordinate this work. An example is the *Arctic Science Funders Forum* which originates from the Arctic Science Ministerial for funders *to initiate and investigate new and enhanced collaborative scientific activities in the Arctic*. It is facilitating *information sharing for information about national and international calls for Arctic research projects and serves as a means to communicate priorities, activities, and opportunities* (<https://iasc.info/cooperations/arctic-science-funders-forum>). Such coordinated funding efforts may want access to an overview of past and present projects within a particular discipline in order to understand where gaps exist or have been closed. The information must be human as well as machine readable.

9. Research infrastructure manager

Research infrastructures are quite commonly concentrated on one discipline, theme or system with some exceptions (e.g. SIOS). The participation on a global level by the fact that not only Arctic nations contribute to Arctic observations. The global perspective is also reflected by the fact that Research Infrastructures or their nodes in the Arctic are commonly part of a distributed RI with stations (or nodes) in the Arctic. For example, the Integrated Carbon Observing System is distributed at the European level with contributing stations (nodes) in the Arctic. From an Arctic perspective these RIs or RI nodes would contribute to the Pan-Arctic observing system. The necessity to participate on a global level reflects also the need for standardization of observations and data level. The same is reflected in Pan-Arctic coverage. In order to plan RI observations, the need to utilize standardisation is highly valuable. Research Infrastructures' nodes are often part of a bigger installation, or site, contribution to many Research Infrastructures or initiatives.

10. Data science

A good principle for data management is that they should be FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Arctic data are maintained at mainly national data centers and are in most cases only FA - Findable and Accessible. Efforts continue in the Arctic data community to promote, identify, and map sources of Arctic data, for instance through the project [Mapping the Polar Data Ecosystem](#). A data scientist may be interested in data sources that are not (yet) captured through such efforts. A data scientist may want access to an overview of projects or programs with Arctic coverage, since the description of these may contain information about new sources of data. The information must be human as well as machine readable.

11. Industry strategist

In contrast with the industry operations use case, industry strategists are envisioned as resource developers or economists assessing the viability of industrial operations in a range of potential operating regions or sites. A specific example would include a team basing decisions about the economic and operational viability of different destination or trans-Arctic shipping routes. Such a group would require long-term climate data record type information covering variables that characterize key aspects of the maritime operating environment, including sea ice concentration and meteorological/oceanographic variables reflecting operational hazards. They may also need to consider the presence and large-scale distribution of protected species, such as marine mammals.

12. Funder interested in a general overview of the field

Funders often are required – either for practical or statutory purposes – to have an overview of the observing activities in the field(s) that they fund. Depending on the reason for this need, the requirements may vary. If the funder needs to know what observing activities are ongoing in their country, the contents and detail needs are quite high, but the participation and coverage requirements may be more limited. If a funder is required to have a broader overview of the observing activities in a particular area, the participation requirements increase but the level of detail may be more moderate. For example, in the US the Arctic Research and Policy Act (ARPA, 1984) requires that the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee maintain an inventory of US observing activities. This, illustrated in the top of the two snowflakes for this use case, is still a very challenging task to accomplish and has yet to be done.

There can be pros and cons to having an inventory like this be publicly accessible: politicians could use the inventory to either justify additional funding for monitoring in the region, or could use the inventory as an argument that there is “too much” observing activity (or otherwise that it is not a good use of taxpayer money) to justify cutting funds.

13. Scientist investigating impacts on mid-latitude systems

Scientists outside of the Arctic often require information about Arctic observations and monitoring programs for their own work. For scientists interested in mid-latitude weather systems, which can be highly influenced by Arctic meteorology and the state of the Arctic sea ice (e.g., Vihma 2014), Arctic observations are critical. That said, without connections and experience in the Arctic observational community, it can be difficult to find what being measured, where those observations are being conducted, and how to access data. A discipline-specific inventory of the atmospheric science measurements across the Arctic would be a valuable resource for someone working in this space, and would help bridge Arctic and non-Arctic research.

14. Defense strategist

One use case that is particularly relevant to the current geopolitical situation is that of a defense strategist. Their primary interest is in who is investing in research capacity and where: their contents needs are primarily related to funders, they have high requirements for completeness, and are most interested in national-level participation. The interests here are not so much in the potential for science or community-relevant information so much as to identify potential foreign intelligence and influence actors working under the guise of scientific observations.

This is a use case that highlights the wide range of potential uses for inventories of observing activities and/or assets. While there is limited appetite among the scientific community to design an inventory with this use case in mind, it is important to keep in mind the range of different ways information that is made available might be used.

15. Emergency Response Manager

This use case relates to information needs of emergency response managers, either at the community or the regional scale. Specific incidents may include a local search and rescue mission or a regional response to impacts of extreme events such as coastal flooding, or wildfires. Also included in the application would be the preparation of community-scale hazard assessment and mitigation plans. Such applications may require information about availability of observational datasets and derived information products, both in near-realtime for use in emergency response situations (e.g., wave buoys, coastal radar) as well as processed datasets for hazard assessment and response planning purposes. For the former case, short term, low-latency access to observational data and data products directly relevant to emergency response situations is critical, as well as accurate and up-to-date information about observing locations and data availability. Data portals ideally would be designed to account for the access needs of emergency responders.

Note: we do not have specification requirements for this use case, so we do not have a snowflake diagram.

Conclusions

For each dimension of requirements, we can look at where all of these different use cases fall in terms of the requirements. Figure 19 shows this, with each of the snowflake diagrams compiled and ordered by the size of inventory necessary for that particular dimension of specification.

For participation, most use cases require national, membership (e.g., SIOS members), or regional (e.g., EU) participation. Relatively few use cases presented here actually require world-wide participation in the inventory effort, likely because the vast majority of Arctic observing efforts come from a relatively small number of nations. Targeted inventory building efforts, focusing on the nations with larger Arctic observing programs, could therefore meet many of the identified needs.

Coverage requirements are largely evenly split between regional (e.g., Svalbard) and pan-Arctic coverage, with a significant number (5) of applications requiring site-level inventories. This suggests a federated system: if inventory information can be made interoperable and sharable, efforts led by sites and regional groups could be fed into a broader tool that spans the Arctic. This requires a significant level of cooperation and standardization that would present a challenge in the present moment, but is not impossible.

Figure 19: The corresponding “limbs” of the snowflake diagrams organized by size of required inventory. Blue markers indicate the level of inventory that is necessary for a particular use case.

Contents requirements are mostly evenly split between disciplinary (e.g., atmospheric/meteorological observations), system (e.g., everything to do with salmon), or comprehensive (limited only by geographic bounds). For very few applications is funder-level contents the appropriate level of scope, which is unfortunate as these are often the most straightforward inventories to build (e.g., the Arctic Observing Viewer, Manley 2015).

Detail requirements mostly fall at the site level, with project-level granularity the second most popular option. For most applications, having precise locations is a key part of using the inventory, and site-level specificity is necessary. Site-level specificity does make the data gathering part of building an inventory particularly challenging, as well as thinking about how to display it. Location information about in situ observations, transects, drifting buoys, and ship or airborne campaigns, potentially combined with the availability of remote sensing products, makes for an enormous database of observations. Network and project level-inventories are effectively an inventory of inventories for most uses described in this paper: to get at the relevant information, users would need to individually explore some number of networks to see whether they meet their information needs.

Present-day observations are by far the most popular requirement for the time dimension, with recent past observations the second most popular. This makes sense: largely, past observational capacity can be found by looking at data repositories rather than at observing capacity inventories. Future or proposed observations can be relevant for planning purposes, but very few people who filled in this survey talked about scenarios related to future planning. Focusing on present, ongoing observations, and keeping observations in the system once they are no longer active (labeled as such) would address most scenarios here.

Completeness specifications rarely require a perfect inventory: having most (~80%) observing efforts in an inventory would address almost all use cases described here. While a true gaps analysis would require a fully comprehensive inventory, most use cases that were described here are not trying to accomplish that. Instead, something is largely better than nothing, and as long as the information included in an inventory meets the needs of the potential users, it is likely that inventories can be used and built out at the same time. The more use, the more incentive there is to make sure your observing assets and capacities are included in the inventory.

In all, we found that there is a wide range of potential uses for observing inventories, ranging from focused, site-level inventories up to broad Pan-Arctic surveys of observing sites. Site-level detail is a key requirement for most use cases, which suggests that might be the starting point for building a sharable standard for observing asset metadata. If a standard can be adopted that facilitates widespread sharing, focused site, regional, and national efforts that meet some of the scenario criteria described above can be built as a starting point towards a pan-Arctic observing inventory. Work is underway to identify and build momentum around that standard (Manley et al, 2026)

The use cases presented here are certainly not a comprehensive list of the ways that an inventory might be used to advance any aspect of work or life related to Arctic observing. The [poll](#) capturing use cases is still open, and the SAON Committee on Networks encourages further input from interested individuals.

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